

Quality of Restaurant in International Centers of Training for International students

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Abstract: This study aims to get the evaluation quality of Restaurant of school for International students in other to reduce some challenges and improve facilities for goods results training. Some criteria have been defined namely: Comfort, Operational Hours, Price, Kindness, Taste, Hygiene, Variety, Healthy, Recommendation, and Preference. Based on this, our simulation has been done on Handong Global University in South Korea on International student. The results show that in general there is some satisfaction for most of them. Students are focus on the price criteria and taste for satisfaction. Others are looking for healthy and variety. But no all criteria can be meeting at the same time. The recommendation was about criteria of ``Variety`` which must be taken in account particularly for improvement. This study can be extending to others internationals universities or schools in general with the same criteria.

Keywords: International students, Quality of restaurant, Level, International Centers of Training (ICoT).

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the world, many students are looking for good universities for many reasons. For certain, it is to reinforce their capacities in a specific domain. For others, it is to get new knowledge with innovative methods learning. The aim is to be competitive on the international market of employment or for government purposes. So, we have the concept of ``Internationals students`` to mention those students coming from others country to learn. They meet some specific challenges as culture, particularly nutrition. So, it is important to help them feel good to perform their purposes. Without satisfaction of food, it will be very difficult to shape themselves in condition of learning for goods results. It is very important to precise that most of them come from others continents. It is to show the gap in field of Culture, so nutrition. ``Most of them are cooking themselves. It could be because in their religion. There are some meals they never eat, the menu is not adapted, the manner to cook is not appreciated, horary of available restaurant are not adapted`` (Johanna Fernández, Joel Ngathe, John Okeme, 2016). Our capacity to adapt to country`s food is challenged. That is why the quality of restaurant is one the big challenge facing. Even in others context where we have many people coming far from different culture, it is important to know how to improve facilities for them. So, that is a current problem facing by people with different culture. Nutrition is only a part of the big challenge on what we are focuses in this article.

So, The main purposes of this article was to get the level of quality of restaurant in the university or school in general, in order to solve this part of problem by providing adapted restaurant regarding the culture of each student. This study is coming in a context of Globalization, when World is seen as one block. We can say this part of problem can be criteria for choosing the international

university. There are some criteria defined for this study: Comfort, Operational Hours, Price, Kindness, Taste, Hygiene, Variety, Healthy, Recommendation, and Preference.

Our methodology developed in this study is the follow:

- A finding of previous research on this topic will be presented with definition of some concepts.
- A background of the study will be done;
- We will proceed to collection of data;
- Analysis of collected Data.
- Next steps will be presentation of results followed by discussion. At the end, all recommendations will be collected.

For simulation, the study will be done in Handong Global University on international students living in international hall. We will collect the data by questionnaires. We choose Population: 193 students living in International Hall Samples: 50 from 27 different countries.

Before all we have to know that mix methodology approach will be applied.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Developed theories:

A study of previous research on the topic shows that a restaurant satisfaction cannot be the same for every customer, while for some people a service can be the best, for others the same service can be the worst. Customer satisfaction can also be defined as satisfaction based on an outcome or a process (Pizam & Ellis, 1999). Using customer satisfaction surveys help to identify bad or

good facts of a specific service and it leads to enhance the quality of service management (Scriabina & Fomichov, 2005). More related theories are developed.

Concerning Customer satisfaction, several definitions and models of customer satisfaction have been proposed by various scholars. The disconfirmation of expectations theory explains that a customer is satisfied when he or she feels that the product's performance is equal to or more than what he or she was expecting. The Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) is commonly used to monitor the successful financial issues of companies and industries. It uses predictive models based on customer expectations, post-consumption perceptions of quality and value (Harr, 2008).

There are different ways to assess the quality of services and customer satisfaction through subjective, or soft, measures of quality. Those ways are focused on perceptions and attitudes of the customer rather than some concrete objective criteria. The soft measures include surveys and questionnaires to determine customer perceptions of the quality of the service they are receiving. If the surveys and questionnaires are properly designed, administered and analyzed, it can be successful to the establishment, because they can improve and it can be the feature that help it to be better than other, by offering a good quality product instead of a mediocre product. In restaurants, if they fail with the process the result will be the lost of customers (Lynn, 2010).

Concerning restaurant quality services, according to some scholars, the service quality involves an attitude and is an evaluation over several service encounters over time. Satisfied customers are integral to the success of a restaurant. Food quality is incredibly important, but there are other factors that also influence in the whole service of a restaurant. The facilities, size and design of a restaurant can make a huge difference. Besides, the operational hours, the price, the kindness of the people working there, the hygiene, and the menu variety; are also very important. All of that together are essential when a customer is about to pick one restaurant. Depending on the restaurant, the definition of quality may be different. An employee's attitude has a strong impact on the customer experience at a restaurant. If the employees approach every situation with a positive, helpful attitude, they will be able to create a pleasant atmosphere even when there are problems (Smith, 2016).

According to the website Restaurant Engine (Restaurant Engine, 2016), there are five main ways to deliver a excellent quality customer service. The first one is "Do it right from the start", this means that is not just food what matters, but also the way the employees receive the customers. The second one is "Do not make them wait", speed of service is vital for a good service. The third one is "Fix problems immediately", the goal of restaurants is to please the customers. The fourth one is "Use Customer Comment Cards", a constant knowledge of customer's opinion is important. The last one is "Incorporate Technology", incorporating technology depends on the restaurant type, but some form of technology can be worked into many restaurant business models.

In the research *The Effect of Service and Food Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Hence Customer Retention* (Ahmad, 2015), the author claimed to investigate the relationships between service quality, food quality, customer satisfaction and customer

retention in limited service restaurants in Jordan. The author did the data collection from 10 different restaurants, a total of 400 questionnaires were distributed equally across these restaurants. The study concluded that both service and food quality would have a positive influence on customer satisfaction, which in turn would positively affect customer retention. Besides, the study proposed that customer satisfaction would mediate the relationship between service quality and customer retention. Finally, the author mentioned that food quality has a great influence on customer satisfaction.

Another research made in a University of Ghana, called *Customer satisfaction and perceptions about food services on the University for Development Studies Campus, Ghana* (Donkoh, Quainoo, Cudjoe, & Kaba, 2012), wanted to know the customer satisfaction and the general perception about food services of two restaurants into the campus. The used a semi-structure questionnaire, then the data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) version 16. They analyzed the frequency each student visited the restaurant, the taste of the food, the price, among others. After the analysis they found a negative relationship between food quality and customer satisfaction, and a positive significant relationship between place and service quality and customer satisfaction. Finally, they also found the challenges that the restaurants faced, and the differences between the both of them.

Another study was made at Oklahoma State University, the title was "Customer Satisfaction, Return Intention, and Word-of-Mouth Endorsement in University Dining Facilities" (Yen, 2005). The author wanted to determine the attributes that can make a customer to have the intention of return, and to determine the influence of food quality, atmosphere, service quality, convenience, and price and value on customer satisfaction, return intention, and word-of-mouth endorsement. The author used questionnaires based on the results of a focus group discussion. The questionnaire had 22 questions about demographic information, perception about food, and overall evaluation of the facilities. The customers were selected randomly from a data base, and the survey was doing using the web. Data was processed and analyzed by the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Window Version 11.5 (SPSS) program. They author concluded that the exterior and interior design of the restaurants is important to attract new customers, and make the old ones to return. In addition, the author said that the managers of the restaurants have to use a customer survey more often.

2.2 Main concepts and definitions

As we were announced before, we have to evaluate the level of quality of each restaurant in Campus of university, in order to get the satisfaction of International students. This lead to hypotheses that " **Level of quality restaurant shapes Satisfaction of International Students**". Our researches questions are:

What are the criteria of best restaurant according to International student's appreciation?

On which particular Criteria University must be focused for improvement?

Customer satisfaction in this study customer satisfaction is the level of satisfaction of International Students in Handong Global

University with the food provided by the four restaurants mentioned in the questionnaire. The Level of satisfaction goes from “Very Unsatisfied”, which means that the student is very disappointed with the restaurant, to “Very Satisfied”, which means that the students enjoy the food, service, or facilities of the restaurant.

Menu Variety claims to find if the restaurants offer many kinds of food, in order to please everyone, by offering many options of different plates.

Quality of Food is focused in the taste of the food, but also in how healthy it is according to the perspective of each student.

International Center of Training (ICoT): it is a center which provides International kind of training to fill the need of world. So the need is not shaped only for a national cause but for others countries cause. We can have university, secondary school, particular center of militaries, and some center with purpose to fulfill need in a particular sector which can attract international students.

3. Results

The results of this survey were presented as follow:

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection was done through a survey based on questionnaires and meeting. We used computer, Smart phone to collect data. As we have précised, the study was done on 50 international students in Handong Global University from 27 countries of 4 different continents. We recorded 4 restaurants: Mom’s Kitchen, Student Cafeteria, Hyoam Restaurant and Farm’s Restaurant. After collection, all data was transcript to Excel boards representing each student with criteria. So, we encountered 50 boards.

2.4 Method of data analysis

Analysis was manually and essentially done with Excel software of Microsoft.

For each criteria we tried to know the level of satisfaction of each students. For each restaurant we tried to resume the level quality. In some way we used mathematics and statistics tools as sum, comparison and in others ways circle diagrams, band diagrams for representation.

Chart 1. Operational Hours Satisfaction

- **Concerning Operational hour:** We noticed that an only total of 10/50 students get totally no satisfaction of the restaurant. So 80 percent are found their way with the operational hours. The less restaurant appreciate is “Student Cafeteria”. The best are “Mom’s Kitchen and Farm’s Restaurant”.

Chart 2. Price Satisfaction

- **Concerning Price:** We noticed that 12/50 students have total dissatisfaction. So 76% found satisfaction on price. The most expensive restaurants are "Hyoam Restaurant and Farm's Restaurant". The less one is Mom's Kitchen.

Chart 3. Taste Satisfaction

- **Concerning Taste:** We noticed that 9/50 students have total dissatisfaction. So 82% found satisfaction on taste. The most feeling restaurant is "Hyoam Restaurant". The less one "Student Cafeteria".

Chart 4. Variety Satisfaction

- **Concerning Variety Satisfaction** We noticed that 18/50 students have total dissatisfaction. So 64 % founds satisfaction on Menu. The most International Restaurant is ``Hyoam Restaurant``. The less one is ``student Cafeteria``.

Chart 5. Healthy Satisfaction

- **Concerning Healthy Satisfaction:** We noticed that 26/50 students have total dissatisfaction. So 48% founds satisfaction on Healthy. The most Healthy Restaurant is ``Hyoam Restaurant``. the less one is `` Farm`s Restaurant``.

Chart 6. Hygiene Satisfaction

- **Concerning Hygiene Satisfaction:** We noticed that 7/50 students have total dissatisfaction. So 86 % founds satisfaction on Hygiene. The most clean Restaurant is `` Farm`s Restaurant``. The less one is ``Student Cafeteria``.

Chart 7. Preference Satisfaction

- **Concerning Preference:** We noticed that the most preferred is ``Mom`s Kitchen`` followed by ` student`s Cafeteria`. The less one is Farm`s Restaurant.

4. Discussions

First of all, we will present recapitulative of all data based on all criteria and all 4 Restaurants described before and then we will Discussed according the summarized result presented and relevance of contrast with diagrams results. Find it in the following table:

Table 1: Summary satisfaction

Criteria	Mom`s Kitchen	Student Cafeteria	Hyoam Restaurant	Farmer`s Restaurant
Comfort	167	153	168	162
Operational Hours	182	143	162	170
Price	181	176	127	134
Kindness	165	162	141	155
Taste	168	146	160	170
Hygiene	161	157	160	166
Variety	149	134	141	151
Healthy	111	98	105	89
Recommend	137	128	128	131
Preference	26	12	11	2
SUMMARY/2150	1447	1309	1303	1330
GENERAL AVERAGE (/100)	67.30	60.88	60.60	61.86
APPRECIATION	FAIRLYWELL	FAIRLYWELL	FAIRLYWELL	FAIRLYWELL

On this table, our focus is only on the first place of each criteria.

- We noticed that Mom`s Kitchen totalize 6/10 criteria. Next we have Farm`s Restaurant with 3/10. After Hyoam`s restaurant is coming. The interpretation is that for **Leadership** that is the classement.
- On second place we have again Mom`s kitchen and Farm`s Restaurant.
- In the same way, the most high number totalized is **182** Operational Hours in Mom`s Kitchen.
- The first place is occupied by these two on 5 common criteria.
- In the part of recommendation, we have the same result.

However, although Good price of Mom`s Kitchen:

- The most comfortable is Hyom`s Restaurant;
- We noticed contrast with **result of variety satisfaction**. The diagram shows that the best is Yoam`s restaurant and the Summary shows that Farmer`s Restaurant is the best. The explanation can be the fact that for ``extreme satisfaction sometime`` we can turn to Hyoam`s Restaurant. But for constantly satisfaction, for long time satisfaction about variety ``**Farm`s Restaurant** is the best choice.
- Another contrast is about **healthy criteria**. On diagram, we can see that Hyoam`s Restaurant is the best (extreme satisfaction and extreme unsatisfaction) But with summarize, the best is Mom`s kitchen. Summary is taking all 5 levels of satisfaction in account. But on diagram, I still focused only on extreme level of satisfaction.

To conclude, we can say that:

- **Mom`s kitchen and Farm`s Restaurant** in General are still be the best and recommended restaurant according to International`s Student;
- Some improvement must be done in all criteria except price and kindness by Cafeteria Restaurant and in price, Comfort and healthy by Hyoam`s Restaurant;
- According to the fact that ``Variety`` is more representative of International students, most of Restaurant must be focused on this criteria by looking best common and healthy culture meal;
- All restaurants have ``fairly`` well appreciation, they have to reach the level of Good or very Good based on improvement of defined criteria;
- For extreme satisfaction diagram result can be taken in account.

5. Conclusions

At the end of our study, we can said that the purposes of define criteria and get quality of all restaurant have been reached. Also regarding questions research, we can answer that:

- Best restaurant is defined by 6/10 criteria which are: Price, preference, recommended, kindness, healthy, operational hours.
- University must be focus especially on ``Variety Criteria`` considered as International criteria as we need to find ourselves in what we eat.

During discussion 5 recommendations have been collected:

- **Mom’s kitchen and Farm’s Restaurant** in General are still be the best and recommended restaurant according to International’s Student;
- Some improvement must be done in all criteria except price and kindness by Cafeteria Restaurant and in price, Comfort and healthy by Hyoam’s Restaurant;
- according to the fact that “Variety” is more representative of International students, most of Restaurant must be focused on this criteria by looking best common and healthy culture meal;
- All restaurants have “fairly” well appreciation, they have to reach the level of Good or very Good based on improvement of defined criteria;
- For extreme satisfaction diagram result can be taken in account.

All defined criteria can be taken in account for further studies concerning restaurant even for Creation of restaurant as it has been done later in Handong.

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1. Al-Tit, A. A. (2015). The effect of service and food quality on customer satisfaction and hence customer retention. *Asian social science, 11*(23), 129.
2. Donkoh, S. A., Quainoo, A. K., Cudjoe, E., & Kaba, N. C. (2012). Customer satisfaction and perceptions about food services on the University for Development Studies Campus, Ghana.
3. Harr, K. K. L. (2008). Service dimensions of service quality impacting customer satisfaction of fine dining restaurants in Singapore.
4. Wickey, J. (2013). Guest Satisfaction Analysis Of A Casual Dining Restaurant: A Comparison Of Tourist Vs Non-tourist Satisfaction Scores.
5. Pizam, A., & Ellis, T. (1999). Customer satisfaction and its measurement in hospitality enterprises. *International journal of contemporary hospitality management, 11*(7), 326-339.
6. Restaurant Engine. (2016, January 12). *5 Ways to Deliver Excellent Customer Service at Your Restaurant*. Retrieved November 25, 2016, from Restaurant Engine: <http://restaurantengine.com/deliver-excellent-customer-service/>
7. Scriabina, N., & Fomichov, S. (2005). 6 ways to benefit from customer complaints. *Quality Progress, 38*(9), 49.
8. Smith, E. (2016). *Service Objectives for a Restaurant*. Retrieved from Chron: <http://smallbusiness.chron.com/service-objectives-restaurant-24914.html>
9. Yen Nee, N. G. (2005). A Study of Customer Satisfaction, Return Intention, and Word-of-Mouth Endorsement in University Dining Facilities. *USA: Thesis for the Degree of Master of Science, Oklahoma State University*.